

Best practice in 'Post-Award' / PM Support in European Research Institutes

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

We are investigating best practice in supporting the full life-cycle of research projects and programmes in universities and research performing organisations (RPOs), from award/initiation to completion and closure.

This questionnaire is intended for anyone who:

- actively supports delivery of projects, programs or portfolios of research in a university or RPO, and
- performs this function at an organisation based in the European Union, EEA, Switzerland or the UK

We expect the results of the study to be published, to help identify improvements to existing processes and explore new models.

The survey should take 15 minutes, and your responses are completely confidential. There will be an option at the end to provide your details should you wish to engage with future research; this information will not be coupled with your answers.

We collect the following data.

- User data: you directly provide most of the data we collect by filling out this survey. We will use this data so we can improve project management for researchers across EU universities. We securely store your data using compliant services procured by our organisation. We will keep your survey response for 12 months maximum to allow the data to be anonymised and studied. Once this period is up, we will delete your original data by discarding all original survey responses, leaving only the anonymised dataset to support future research publications.

To make sure you are fully aware of all of your data protection rights, every user is entitled to the following:

- The right to request copies of your personal data
- The right to correct any information you believe is inaccurate. You also have the right to request our organization to complete the information you believe is incomplete
- The right to request that our organization erase your personal data, under certain conditions
- The right to restrict the processing of your personal data, under certain conditions
- The right to object to our organization's processing of your personal data, under certain conditions

- The right to request that our organization transfer the data that we have collected to another organization, or directly to you, under certain conditions

If you have any questions about the survey, please contact us. We really appreciate your input!

* I am based in the EU, EEA, Switzerland or the UK

- Yes
- No

* I understand and accept the conditions and am ready to start the survey

- Yes
- No

Thank you for your time - this survey is not aimed at you.

About You

What is your job title?

Which would best describe your role?

- I am directly assigned to one or more active projects or programs
- I support active projects, as part of a project management or departmental administrative unit
- I support active projects, as part of a functional office (e.g. finance, contracts, HR)
- I am a senior executive / director with oversight on active projects
- Other

Please describe your role

Is your position

- Permanent contract
- Temporary contract (fixed term)
- Temporary contract (project specific)

What is the highest education qualification you hold?

- School leaver qualifications
- Undergraduate degree or equivalent
- Masters degree or equivalent
- Doctorate or equivalent

Do you hold any of the following certifications related to project or business management?

- PMI "CAPM"
- PMI "PMP"
- Prince2
- MBA
- Other

Please state the other.

How long have you been performing your current role?

- Less than a year
- 1 - 2 years
- 2 - 4 years
- 4 - 8 years
- Over 8 years

Since achieving your highest educational qualification, have you had previous experience...

- working as a professional researcher, eg. a postdoc or academic
- working in research, in a company
- working in another type of role in a company
- working in the public sector
- working for another type of non-profit organisation

Are you an individual member or affiliated with...

- EARMA
- BestPrac (COST Actions)
- PMI (global)
- PMI (local chapter)
- Other

Please state the other.

Is your organisation a member of / affiliated with...

- EARMA
- INORMS
- LERU
- Coimbra Group
- Other

Please state the other.

Which country are you based in?

Are you...

- Male
- Female
- Other / Prefer not to say

Features of Post-award support in your organisation

Which of these functions do you perform for projects/programs in your organisation?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Frequently
Report project status to senior managers or boards	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Support cost monitoring in projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Monitor and control project performance (not just financial)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Operate a project information system or dashboard	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Develop and implement a standard methodology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Promote project management within organisation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Develop competence of team members, including training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provide mentoring for other project managers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provide project management tools without trying to standardise their use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coordinate between projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Identify, select and prioritize new projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provide input to strategic planning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Support results exploitation and dissemination	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Track my own performance against objectives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conduct post-project reviews	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Manage a database of lessons learned	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Actively monitor project financial risks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Implement a general risk database (not just financial)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Manage archives of project documentation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Execute specialised tasks on behalf of project leads	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Manage partner or sponsor interfaces	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Take part in recruitment for project managers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Does your organisation have:

- a single central office with overall responsibility for project management support
- a central office that distributes responsibility to local offices that provide project management support
- single or small teams of staff providing localised support to specific projects /programs
- none of the above

Is project support in your organisation...

- mainly a 'personal' service, with contact between support staff and researchers / project leads
- mainly based on provision of templates, forms and processes, without personal interaction
- fairly evenly balanced between personal and non-direct service

Is the level of support received by your projects/programs dependent on their funding source?

- All receive a standard support service
- Some receive preferential support, for strategic or other known reason
- The level of support varies, without a specific reason I can identify
- I am not aware of any variations between projects

How would you best describe the way project support is paid for in your organisation? (select all that apply)

- Directly charged to project budgets as a fixed cost
- Directly charged to project budgets, based on a structured cost model
- Directly charged to project budgets, on bespoke service agreements
- Indirectly funded from project-derived overheads / indirect costs
- Indirectly funded from non-project derived funds (e.g. central or core funding)

How long has this system or office been in operation in its current form? (to the nearest number of years).

Only values of at least 0 are allowed

 years

And a little more about how projects are supported:

How is information on the status of your projects/programs provided to senior members of your organisation?

- I collect status information, analyze it and provide reports to senior management / sponsors and inform them if there are specific problems requiring their attention
- Status information is collected, reported and distributed to senior management / sponsors but I am not responsible for analysis or defining corrective actions
- Nobody performs this function

When conducting post-reviews of project performance (lessons learned)...

- I do not conduct reviews
- I facilitate the process of capturing lessons learned, as part of routine project meetings and events
- I facilitate the process, analyze / consolidate outcomes, and generate proposals for continuous improvement

Consider relationships between projects and programs you support:

- There is no systematic effort made to identify interactions
- Interactions are identified between projects and programs of the department when they start, but little further monitoring takes place
- Interactions/interdependencies are identified between projects and programs, triggering action from project leads and stakeholders if/when required

How is your project management methodology developed and implemented?

- There is no standard methodology
- We have developed a basic methodology, but it is not used consistently on all projects
- We have developed a standard methodology, aligning possible existing methodologies in different areas, and the methodology is used in most projects

How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I often need support to perform project management	<input type="radio"/>				
I can find support easily when I need it	<input type="radio"/>				
Leadership from senior level drives success in our projects	<input type="radio"/>				
There is a lack of buy-in for project management support	<input type="radio"/>				
The practice of project management in my team / department is mature	<input type="radio"/>				
Project management across my organisation is mature	<input type="radio"/>				
Support personnel normally perform a variety of functions	<input type="radio"/>				
Roles and responsibility within support teams are clearly defined	<input type="radio"/>				
There is active quality management (at some level)	<input type="radio"/>				
More resources, funding, and direction are needed for project support	<input type="radio"/>				
Projects often proceed according to schedule	<input type="radio"/>				

I have clear lines of decision making and escalation	<input type="radio"/>				
Project managers have specialized tasks /responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>				
Processes are continuously being reviewed and improved	<input type="radio"/>				
The tools and processes provided are effective	<input type="radio"/>				

About systems and tools

Which of these tools are used in your organisation for project management?

- Basic Microsoft Office apps (Excel etc)
- G-suite applications
- Microsoft Project
- Advanced Microsoft data apps (Power BIU, Power Query, Flow etc)
- Microsoft Sharepoint / Teams
- Dropbox
- EMDesk
- Slack
- Oracle
- SAP
- Trello
- In-house bespoke solution
- Other Enterprise / Resource Management solution or app

(please state)

Does your organisation provide project management training, following a standard methodology?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Is that methodology applied to your projects?

- Always
- Often
- Rarely
- Never

Does your organisation have a framework to evaluate how your system of project-management support aligns with its objectives?

- Yes

- No
- I don't know

Any final thoughts?

What opportunities for improvement are there in the way in which your organisation supports its research projects?

What barriers exist in implementing post-award management in your organisation?